

Preventing heat stress in layer systems with covered veranda and outdoor access

ANIVET

Heat stress in laying hens – a welfare challenge

Heat stress in laying hens occurs when they are unable to physiologically or behaviourally keep their body temperature below the upper limit of their thermo-neutral zone. Reaching the limit depends on the temperature-humidity index, the duration of the heat challenge, the housing conditions and characteristics of the hen (e.g., hydration status, genotype and degree of acclimatisation). Typically the recommended indoor ambient temperature is between 18 and 24 °C.

Heat stress is a welfare challenge in laying hens. When exposed to heat stress, the laying hens will seek to minimise internal heat production by reducing feed intake and locomotor activity. Water intake will increase. To promote heat dissipation, they will hold their wings away from the body and start panting, i.e., short and quick breaths with open beak. High humidity reduces the effectiveness of panting, so hot and humid conditions are more challenging than hot and dry conditions.

Figure 1: Laying hen (left) panting and holding the wings away from the body due to heat stress.

Source: ANIVET

If the heat stress is prolonged, body weight, egg production rate and egg weight will be reduced. If the attempt to cope with the heat stress fails, body temperature will rise, which may lead to lethargy and eventually death.

Legal requirements

Council directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purpose:

“Air circulation, dust levels, temperature, relative air humidity and gas concentrations must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals.”
(Annex, Point 10)

How to prevent heat stress in laying hens

Good practices for preventing heat stress in laying hens are described below. They are targeting closed environmentally controlled houses, although some may also be relevant for open naturally ventilated houses. The focus of the factsheet is on hens kept in systems with covered veranda and/or outdoor access, but some of the described good practices are also relevant for hens kept indoor only.

Use tunnel ventilation and cooling pads

The tunnel ventilation system is based on a negative-pressure system arising when the air enters the house at one end of the building and exits at the other end

Laying hens: Preventing heat stress in systems with covered veranda and outdoor access

via large exhaust fans. Due to the high rate of air exchange and movement, this type of ventilation system is considered the most effective in heat management. The recommended air speed during the hottest period is 2.5-3 m/s, and it should be adjusted automatically in relation to the indoor temperature and humidity.

For further effectiveness, tunnel ventilation can be combined with cooling pads on hot summer days. A cooling pad consists in a layer of wet pads ("sponges") that air from the outside passes through when drawn into the barn. This makes the air more humid but cooler since humid air contains more thermal energy than air of the same temperature with lower humidity. The lower the outdoor humidity, the more effective the cooling pads are, i.e., the evaporative cooling principle works especially good in hot and dry environments.

Figure 2: Cooling pads seen from the covered veranda outside the barn. Source: ANIVET

Manage popholes according to indoor climate

If the laying hens have access to a veranda or outdoor range, it may be impossible to keep the indoor temperature at a level that allows the hens to remain in their thermal comfort zone during very hot weather conditions. The reason for this is that when the popholes are open, negative pressure is lost and the effectiveness of the ventilation is reduced.

Closing the popholes during the hottest period of the day is therefore recommended. An example coming from a layer farm located in a hot and dry climate area in Spain is to have open popholes in the morning (8:00-11:00) and again in the late evening (20:00-22:30;

sunset: 22:00). The indoor temperature is influenced, but only to a degree that can be counteracted by increasing the airspeed of the ventilation. In the example, lights are on during 6:00-22:00, allowing the birds to feed and lay eggs before the popholes open.

Each pophole should be adjustable independently of the others to enable that some can be closed while others are open to reduce the loss of the negative pressure in the barn if needed. This should be done automatically according to the indoor temperature and humidity.

The timetable for access to the covered veranda or outdoor range should be adjusted regularly according to the sunrise/sunset changes.

Figure 3: Popholes should be independently adjustable. Source: ANIVET

Provide plenty of cold drinking water

Cold drinking water should always be available, as this can reduce the body temperature of the laying hens. To accomplish that, the water tanks need to be insulated, light coloured, shaded and filled up to at least 80% capacity. The pipes from the tank into the barn should be running 1-2 m underground or be well insulated. Alternatively, the water tank may be bypassed during hot periods, such that water is led directly to the drinkers to avoid the risk that it heats up in the tank. Inside the barn, the pipes should be well distanced from the roof and regularly flushed to keep the water cool.

As the birds will drink more when exposed to high temperatures, more drinker space is needed compared to normal situations.

Laying hens: Preventing heat stress in systems with covered veranda and outdoor access

Minimise heat absorption from the roof and walls

Insulation of the roof minimises heat absorption during sunny days and has the advantage of also being a benefit during winter as it will keep the air at a higher temperature, reducing moist formation.

The slope of the roof should be rather flat to avoid warm air accumulating under the roof inside the barn.

If there is no covered veranda attached to the barn, then the roof should have an overhang as this will help preventing direct and indirect sunlight from entering the barn.

The roof may also be equipped with roof sprinklers as spraying water on the roof in hot and dry climates can contribute to cooling the barn. However, the effect depends, among other things, on the degree of insulation.

Provide a properly designed covered veranda

A covered veranda functions as a large overhang and therefore prevents direct and indirect sunlight on the side wall, which reduces the heat absorbed into the barn.

Curtains on the outer wall of the veranda function to cool the veranda, though the effect depends on the orientation of the barn.

Curtains should be at least partly drawn to shield against the sun during the hottest period of the day.

Figure 4: The curtain at the back (where the pipe goes through) is drawn to shield against the sun, whereas the curtain in front (where the wire netting is visible) is open. Source: ANIVET

Reduce stocking density

At lower stocking densities, there will be a greater airflow between the hens, allowing the heat radiating from the body of the hens to dissipate. Contrarily, at higher stocking densities, the heat accumulates between the birds, causing a temperature increase.

An alternative to reducing the stocking density by placing fewer individuals is to attract birds to the covered veranda and/or the outdoor range when access is possible. This reduces the indoor stocking density. Attractiveness may be increased by adding perches, foraging material and shelter, preferably in terms of natural vegetation including bushes and trees. The latter also create shaded areas, reducing the risk of heat stress even further.

Other practices reducing the risk of heat stress

- More heat stress resistant genotypes of laying hens should be chosen for high-risk areas.
- If the laying hens must be handled, this should be done during the coolest period of the day.
- Peak time of digestion, and hence internal heat production, is 8 h after feeding. During extreme heat waves, a strategy could be to take this into consideration in the feeding schedule.
- Indoor foggers may decrease the ambient indoor temperature, but they are ineffective and cause negative welfare issues if not correctly installed and managed.

Co-funded by
the European Union

AARHUS UNIVERSITY

IZSLER